

EuroFAANG

Accelerating genome to phenome research
for farmed animals in Europe

EuroFAANG is an internationally coordinated effort to unravel the connection between the genetic make-up of farmed animals and their observable physical and physiological traits. EuroFAANG currently comprises of six research projects and one infrastructure project funded by the EU.

The EuroFAANG Research Infrastructure (RI) project works on developing and conceptualising a framework of knowledge hubs, repositories, biobanks and experimental facilities to realise the full potential of Genotype-to-Phenotype (G2P) research across species. The EuroFAANG RI project aims to streamline interdisciplinary capabilities for G2P research in terrestrial and aquatic farmed animals and provide further transnational access to all the relevant facilities, expertise and knowledge to European stakeholders in the future. It draws on the research infrastructures available in the initial project group and aims to expand from there.

The EuroFAANG community is supported by seven projects

Documenting genome function to understand the basis for trait variation and disease resistance in farmed fish.

www.aqua-faang.eu

Identifying genome features driving phenotypic diversity in cattle.

www.bovreg.eu

Developing new breeding strategies to help ruminants adapt to climatic changes.

www.rumigen.eu

Understanding microbiomes of ruminant holobiont.

www.holoruminant.eu

Identifying genome features whose activity, during development and when facing environmental challenges, determines complex traits in chicken and pigs.

www.gene-switch.eu

Providing new knowledge and tools for genome and epigenome enabled breeding in monogastrics.

www.geronimo-h2020.eu

Streamlining interdisciplinary capabilities for G2P research in terrestrial and aquatic farmed animals.

www.eurofaang.eu

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation and Horizon Europe programmes under the Grant Agreements no 817923, 815668, 817998, 101000236, 101000226, 101094718 and 101094718.

EuroFAANG

IMPACT OF THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

This interdisciplinary initiative merges genomics, breeding, phenotyping, and animal health expertise, fostering collaboration and propelling farmed animal science in Europe

RESEARCH AIMS:

- Increase efficiency through precision breeding
- Increase disease resistance
- Minimise environmental impact

JOINT STRATEGIES:

- Communication and dissemination
- Training
- Research Methodology

- 1 Maximising User Engagement
- 2 Unraveling Complex Breeding Traits
- 3 Understanding Genomic Regulation
- 4 Improved Prediction Models
- 5 Addressing Global Challenges

IMPACT

RESEARCH AND ACADEMIA

EuroFAANG RI streamlines expertise, facilities, and knowledge hubs to boost genome-to-phenome (G2P) research across species. It optimizes interdisciplinary capabilities in livestock research, offering European stakeholders access to essential resources. By supporting G2P livestock research, it fosters cutting-edge science and user-defined priorities.

BIOBANKS AND LABORATORIES

EuroFAANG RI plans to create a centralized web portal for easy access to resources, including samples, data, and results. This portal will also facilitate transnational access to institutions and reference samples, such as organoids and stem cells

POLICYMAKERS

The project tackles farm animal production challenges in line with the Farm to Fork strategy of the Green Deal. This involves optimizing resource usage, enhancing animal health and welfare through faster breeding advancements, and addressing breeding's climate impact. The findings can inform policy decisions.

BREEDERS

The project's G2P research can help breeders understand the link between the genetic makeup of animals and their observable physical and physiological traits. This knowledge can inform and adapt breeding decisions and strategies more quickly to future challenges.

WELFARE AND ETHICS EXPERTS, HIGHER EDUCATION PROVIDERS

EuroFAANG RI is setting up a gene editing think-tank with genome editing, ethics, and animal breeding experts across Europe. This initiative will help ensure that the project's research and outcomes align with ethical standards and contribute to animal welfare.

In 2023, the **EuroFAANG Research Infrastructure (RI)** became the first RI to join the EuroFAANG cluster. Currently, in its **conceptual stage**, EuroFAANG RI is establishing the foundation for a comprehensive research infrastructure. The goal is to enhance our knowledge of animal genetics and characteristics by connecting genomics and phenomics in farmed animal species.

Common Data Structure and Access

European Framework for Biobanking

KEY OBJECTIVES

Improving Breeding, Phenotyping and Genomic Technologies

Integration with existing Projects and Infrastructures

The EuroFAANG RI (2023–2025)

aims to establish a sustainable pan-European infrastructure for **genotype-to-phenotype (G2P)** research in diverse farmed animal species.

The EuroFAANG community is composed of:

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LEARN MORE

The EuroFAANG RI project has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101094718.